

STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY ASSESSMENT OF REPURPOSED EOL WIND TURBINE BLADE COMPOSITE COMPONENTS USING ACOUSTIC EMISSION TESTING AND *IB*-VALUE ANALYSIS UNDER VARIOUS LOADING AND TEMPERATURE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Wind energy is an essential renewable energy source; however, the disposal of end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blades (WTBs) presents significant challenges. Repurposing EoL WTB components, such as spar caps, for use in the construction sector is a sustainable alternative; however, pre-existing damage can affect their mechanical performance. This study investigates an acoustic emission (AE)-based approach that incorporates improved *b*-value (*Ib*-value) analysis to assess the structural integrity of EoL WTB spar cap specimens. Tensile and bending tests are performed at 23 °C and 67 °C to evaluate damage propagation for potential construction applications. AE data analysis confirmed the method's effectiveness in detecting early degradation. Furthermore, the influence of temperature on the mechanical properties of the composite material is investigated. The findings indicate that *Ib*-value analysis is a viable non-destructive testing method for assessing structural repurposed EoL WTB components under various loading conditions. The extension of this approach to other EoL WTB components has the potential to enhance circular economy strategies in the wind energy and construction sectors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wind power is a crucial renewable energy source, with a substantial volume of end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blade (WTB) material anticipated globally by 2050 [1], with Germany contributing a major share [2]. However, the management of EoL WTBS poses significant challenges due to the

environmental impact of disposal [3]. The utilization of composites as the primary material in WTBs is predominantly attributable to their high specific mechanical properties [4]. However, their thermoset-based polymer matrix makes recycling difficult [5]. Under circular economy principles [6], the repurpose strategy offers a promising alternative [7-9], especially for structural components of EoL WTBs [10]. By repurposing EoL WTB composite components in a second life application with a new function, this strategy seeks to extend the service life of the composite materials while preserving their structural integrity. Unidirectional (UD) reinforced spar cap beams, which are characterized by their excellent mechanical properties, are assumed to be suitable for repurposing in large quantities in various industrial sectors, including the construction industry. However, the possibility of pre-existing damage resulting from the manufacturing process or the first life cycle cannot be discounted, as this may lead to mechanical degradation [11]. Understanding these effects and defining their reliability is essential for the structural repurpose of EoL WTB components in second-life applications.

Previous research has presented a method for assessing the structural integrity of composite components using acoustic emission (AE) testing combined with *Ib*-value analysis [12, 13]. AE is a well-established, non-destructive testing (NDT) technology with high resolution. The *b*-value analysis, which monitors the cumulative amplitude distribution, demonstrated sufficient feasibility with modification. The improved *b*-value (*Ib*-value) was combined to assess the structural integrity of EoL WTB spar cap specimens [14]. The method has been studied and concluded to be effective in identifying early damage propagation under tensile loading at room temperature (RT).

However, the robustness of this technique for other loading conditions and at elevated temperatures (ET) remains to be validated. This study explores the feasibility of *Ib*-value analysis for tensile and bending loading at ET conditions, considering repurpose in the construction sector. The ET of 67 °C is determined in accordance with a German guideline (*BUEV recommendations*) that holds validity in the construction sector. To this end, tensile and bending tests are carried out at RT (23 °C) and ET (67 °C). The AE data collected during these tests are used to perform a comparative behavior analysis of the tensile and bending specimens at RT and ET. The present study focuses on the *b*/*Ib*-value analysis to evaluate the reliability of this method in different loading scenarios.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and EoL WTB specimen preparation

An EoL WTB (E40 wind turbine; Enercon, Germany) with a service life of approximately 20 years is used as the base material in this study. The WTB extends along a longitudinal direction (LD) measuring 19.3 m, while the transverse direction (TD) is perpendicular to the LD, with a maximum width of 1.92 m (Figure 1a). The spar cap component (Figure 1a, Section A-A), consists of glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites. The extraction of UD GFRP spar cap samples is conducted in alignment with the sectioning approach described by Joustra *et al.* [10].

Initially, TD cuts are performed using a wire saw to separate the EoL WTB segments (Figure 1a, dashed lines). Subsequent to this, LD cuts are performed to extract the shear web and sandwich elements from the spar cap beams (Figure 1b). The spar cap beams are then cut (Figure 1c) into square-shaped components measuring 200 mm in length (Figure 1d) and are further processed into tensile and bending specimens. Consequently, one side of each spar cap component is flattened with a CNC router, following the process of wheel cutting to obtain samples with a thickness of 4 mm. Any sharp edges are smoothed with sandpaper. For tensile testing, 1.6 mm thick GFRP tabs are bonded to 50 mm of both ends of each tensile sample using an epoxy film adhesive (UCS-I-95; UCS, China), resulting in a gauge length of 100 mm. The final tensile specimens have overall dimensions of 200 x 20 x 4 mm (Figure 1e). The specimens for the bending tests are produced from the tensile specimens through the use of a waterjet machine and measure 80 x 20 x 4 mm (Figure 1f). The glass fiber volume fraction of the UD specimens is estimated to be approximately 43.9% (density glass fiber: 2.48 g/cm³, density matrix: 1.19 g/cm³). As the tests are planned at ET, the glass transition temperature of the matrix material is determined to be 100 °C using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in accordance with ISO 11357.

Figure 1: Preparation process of EoL spar cap specimens: (a) EoL WTB; (b) EoL WTB segment; (c) Spar cap beam; (d) Square-shaped spar cap component; (e) Dimensions of tensile specimens and sensor locations; (f) Dimensions of bending specimens and sensor locations.

2.2 Material characterization at different temperatures

The mechanical properties of the prepared EoL specimens are evaluated through tensile and bending tests performed at two different temperatures: room temperature (RT, 23 °C) and elevated temperature (ET, 67 °C). Tensile tests are conducted following the standards outlined in ASTM D3039 and are carried out on a universal testing machine equipped with a temperature chamber (Instron 5985; Instron, USA) at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min (Figure 2a). The selection of this strain rate is driven by the objective of minimizing the strong overlap of AE signals, especially after 50 % of the specimen life when signal density increases significantly. In order to reduce measurement noise, neither an extensometer nor a strain gauge is used. A minimum of seven tensile specimens are tested at each temperature condition. In addition, bending tests are conducted at RT and ET, following ASTM D790, and are performed on a universal testing machine equipped with a temperature chamber (Instron 5985; Instron, USA) at a crosshead speed of 0.9 mm/min (Figure 2b). The span length is 33.6 mm. A minimum of six bending specimens are tested at each temperature condition. AE monitoring is performed simultaneously during the material characterization tests.

Figure 2: (a) Tensile test equipment; (b) Bending test equipment.

2.3 Acoustic emission testing

Wide-range piezoelectric AE sensors (IDK-AES-H150; IDK Co., Ltd., Republic of Korea) with a frequency range of 100-900 kHz were used for AE monitoring. During both tensile and bending tests, two AE sensors are attached to each specimen and secured with silicone grease (HIVAC-G; Shin-Etsu, Japan) and vinyl tape (Figure 2a and Figure 2b). The locations of the sensors (S1 and S2) are labeled "S" in Figure 1e and Figure 1f. The sensor placement remained constant throughout all experiments for both testing temperatures.

Before the experiments, the sensitivity of both AE sensors is verified. The AE signals are amplified using preamplifiers (IDK-AMP-S001-40/60; IDK Co. Ltd., Republic of Korea) with a gain of 40 dB_{AE}. During the testing phase, AE signals exceeding the 40 dB_{AE} threshold are detected with a digitizer (IDK-DAQ8; IDK Co. Ltd., Republic of Korea) at a sampling rate of 5 MSPS per channel. The AE signals are recorded under the conditions listed in Table 1. The time parameters are set as follows: peak definition time (PDT) at 200 μs, hit definition time (HDT) at 400 μs, and hit lockout time (HLT) at 4000 μs. Additionally, the amplitude, energy, and frequency characteristics of the AE signals are calculated and recorded, with the centroid frequency serving as the primary frequency characteristic for GFRP. AE signal analysis is based on key features including raw amplitude, hit frequency (hits per second), and AE frequency (peak frequency). Data processing is carried out using MATLAB software (version R2024a, MathWorks, USA).

	Threshold	Pre-amplifier	Sampling conditions		
			Sampling rate	Pre-trigger	Length ¹
Value	40	40	5	100	1000
Unit	dB _{AE}	dB _{AE}	MSPS	μs	μs

¹Length: Recording time for each acoustic emission (AE) signal after the AE signal exceeds a certain threshold.

Table 1: Acoustic emission testing conditions.

As shown in previous studies, the dominant failure modes in UD reinforced specimens include matrix cracking, interfacial failure, and fiber breakage/fracture [15]. In FRPs, AE signals typically fall within the 100 kHz to 600 kHz range when a band-pass filter is applied, with specific frequency ranges corresponding to distinct fracture modes. High frequencies (400 - 600 kHz) are indicative for fiber breakage/fracture, low frequencies (100 - 220 kHz) correspond to matrix cracking, and intermediate frequencies (220 - 400 kHz) are associated with interfacial failure mechanisms. Multiple specimens are tested under each temperature condition (tensile and bending), resulting in minimal variation in AE parameters and characteristics. This reproducibility enabled the selection of a representative dataset for further analysis.

2.4 *b-Ib*-value analysis

For *b-Ib*-value analysis, the amplitude of AE signals is recorded, and the cumulative distribution function (CDF) is plotted according to Equation (1):

$$N(A) = \int_A^{\infty} n(A')dA' \quad (1)$$

here, A denotes a specific amplitude, while A' is an auxiliary amplitude variable used for integration, n(A') is the number of AE hits corresponding to each particular amplitude, and N(A) represents the cumulative number of hits with amplitudes equal to or greater than A. Although A' is mathematically equivalent to A, the distinction is introduced for notational clarity. In AE analysis, the amplitude A [dB_{AE}] is defined by Equation (2), using a reference voltage 1 μV as V₀.

$$A = 20 * \log_{10} \frac{V_1}{V_0} \quad (2)$$

The concept of b -value was introduced by Gutenberg through the Gutenberg-Richter equation, which is defined as the negative slope of the CDF, as shown in Equation (3). Originally developed for seismological analysis, this method has also been applied to materials such as concrete [16].

$$\log_{10} * N(A) = a - bA \quad (3)$$

where a is an empirical constant, and b is the b -value, representing the slope of the linear relationship, typically determined by the least-square method. The b -value remains positive as long as the CDF shows a declining trend. In the early damage phase, dominated by microcracking, many low-amplitude and few high-amplitude AE signals are recorded, resulting in a high b -value (green line, Figure 3a). As macrocracks develop, the number of high-amplitude AE signals increases, shifting the CDF and reducing the b -value (orange line, Figure 3a) [17]. This decline near failure indicates that the b -value effectively reflects structural health. In composite materials, where multiple cracks propagate independently, tracking major crack regions using the mean value (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of AE amplitudes is more practical. This localized form of analysis, known as the Ib -value, was introduced by Shiotani [18] and further studied by Jung and Na [12]. The Ib -value is described in Equation (4):

$$\log_{10} * N(A) = a - IbA \dots (\mu - \alpha_1\sigma < A < \mu + \alpha_2\sigma) \quad (4)$$

α_1 and α_2 are constants defining the lower ($\mu - \alpha_1\sigma$) and upper ($\mu + \alpha_2\sigma$) amplitude limits (Figure 3b). The amplitude range is $(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)\sigma$, typically with an $\alpha_1:\alpha_2$ ratio of 1:1 or 1:2; in this study, both were set to 1. The parametric values are calculated after every 500 AE hits for the tensile specimens and after every 100 AE hits for the bending specimens (i.e., 1st to 100/500th, 1st to 200/1000th, ..., up to 400/2000th). The slopes of b -/ Ib -values are determined using the least-squares method. High values indicate a dominance of microscopic fractures, while low values suggest increasing macroscopic fracture activity (i.e., large amplitude signals).

Figure 3: (a) Interpretations and (b) Definition of b -/ Ib -value analysis [14].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Analysis of the failure behavior of the EoL spar cap composites at RT and ET

Tensile loading: The RT tensile specimens show an average ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of 683 MPa, while the ET specimens exhibit a slightly lower average UTS of 598 MPa. The UTS represents 100 % of the tensile specimen lifetime and marks the point of total failure. At both test temperatures, the tensile specimens exhibit linear elastic stress-strain behavior until they reach total failure. The influence of different temperature settings on material behavior under tensile loading is explored in the frequency domain. Figures 4a and 4b present the acoustic emission (AE) frequency analysis results for the RT and ET specimens, respectively.

Figure 4: Centroid frequency range as the total hits for (a) RT and (b) ET tensile specimens.

The overall frequency range is broad; however, distinct preferred centroid frequency ranges are identified. For both RT and ET specimens, high frequencies (400 – 600 kHz) associated with fiber breakage are dominant. As the specimen’s approach total failure, a significant number of intermediate (220 – 400 kHz) and low frequency (100 – 220 kHz) hits are detected. In particular, the RT specimens exhibited a significantly higher number of mid-frequency hits (corresponding to interfacial failure) compared to the ET specimens from 20% lifetime onward. This trend is also illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: AE distribution showing the centroid frequency at RT and ET (each AE hit fraction was normalized to the total number of AE hits).

In the context of ET, the polymer matrix undergoes partial softening, resulting in a reduction of its load-carrying capacity and the appearance of slight ductility. These two effects have opposing implications for interfacial adhesion: softening tends to weaken the interface, while increased ductility may enhance it. However, the overall impact appears to be dominated by the negative influence of matrix softening. Considering the significant mismatch in mechanical properties between the fibers and the matrix, as well as the intrinsic brittleness of the fibers, the potential benefits of increased ductility appear to be negligible in tensile specimens loaded in LD.

Bending loading: The RT bending specimens exhibit an average ultimate flexural strength (UFS) of 1,174 MPa, while the ET specimens show a reduced average UFS of 890 MPa. UFS is defined as the maximum bending load a specimen can sustain before complete structural failure. Although the EoL bending specimens display a moderate reduction in bending strength under ET conditions, their mechanical performance remains comparatively high. Analogous trends are observed in the tensile specimens tested at ET. These findings underscore the viability of repurposing EoL spar cap components in structural second life applications, including those exposed to ET, such as in the construction sector.

Figures 6a and 6b present representative stress–strain curves and trend lines under bending load, along with corresponding AE hits in the frequency domain. Up to approximately 60% of the specimen's lifetime, both curves exhibit a similar slope ($b_{RT1} = b_{ET1}$), indicating comparable stiffness during the initial loading phase. Beyond this point, a reduction in slope is observed ($b_{RT2} < b_{RT1}$; $b_{ET2} < b_{ET1}$), particularly in the ET specimens. The secondary linear slope (b_{ET2}) is lower than that of the RT specimens (b_{RT2}), which may contribute to the lower UFS under ET conditions.

The AE data also reflect this transition. During the initial 60% of the lifetime, the AE signals predominantly lie within a narrow frequency range of 400–600 kHz for RT and ET bending specimens, a range associated with fiber breakage. After this point, the frequency distribution becomes significantly broader. In addition to high-frequency events, intermediate- and low-frequency AE hits (100–400 kHz) are increasingly apparent, suggesting the onset of additional damage mechanisms such as matrix cracking or interfacial debonding.

Figure 6: Centroid frequency range as total hits for (a) RT bending and (b) ET bending specimens.

Fundamentally, since tensile failure dominates in this material system, the AE distribution of centroid frequencies observed under bending closely resembles that observed in tensile failure. The centroid frequency ranges remain generally similar for the bending specimens tested at both temperatures. Notably, the ET specimens exhibit a slightly higher number of high-frequency AE hits compared to those tested at RT. This trend is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: AE distribution for both bending temperatures (each AE hit fraction was normalized to the total number of AE hits).

3.2 *b*-/*Ib*-value analysis of tensile and bending tests at different temperatures

The *b*-/*Ib*-value analysis uses data from the first 30% of the specimen's lifetime to ensure sufficient AE activity and to allow the specimen to undergo complex microdamage behavior in the early stages. This period typically exhibits numerous microcracks and rising *b*-values, which do not reliably indicate structural integrity. To improve data quality, the first 50 AE hits—primarily considered noise—are excluded from the analysis.

As shown in Figure 8, the *b*-value does not exhibit a consistent trend over the lifetime of the tensile and bending specimens tested at RT and ET. Depending on the loading condition, the *b*-value either increases or decreases, indicating variability rather than a clear progression. This inconsistency suggests a potential overemphasis of micro-cracks activity in the results. Consequently, the *b*-value is not considered valid as a reliable indicator in terms of SHM purposes.

Figure 8: Lifetime dependence of *b*-values during tensile and bending tests at RT and ET.

The Ib -value analysis presented in Figure 9 shows a decreasing trend for both tensile and bending specimens, indicating greater reliability as a damage assessment criterion. It demonstrates potential for representing the structural health of EoL composite materials.

The final Ib -value for the tensile tests (Figure 9a) ranges from 0.05 to 0.055 at RT, and increases slightly to approximately 0.06 under ET conditions. This increase may result from temperature-induced changes in the matrix properties or a weakened fiber-matrix interface.

In bending tests (Figure 9b), the final Ib -value ranges from 0.055 to 0.06 at RT and increases slightly to approximately 0.065 under ET conditions. At both temperatures, the Ib -value exhibits a two-phase trend: a typical decreasing phase followed by a slower decreasing phase beginning at approximately 60% of the specimen's lifetime. This transition corresponds to the change in slope observed in the stress-strain response, indicating a shift from major crack propagation to the final failure phase, which is characterized by the formation of numerous microcracks. Sudden jumps in the Ib -value are likely caused by the abrupt formation of individual microcracks.

Figure 9: Lifetime dependence of Ib -values during (a) tensile tests at RT and ET and (b) bending tests at RT and ET.

3.3 Comparison Ib -value analysis for tensile and bending specimens

The Ib -value is found to be sensitive to varying loading conditions. Therefore, its interpretation as an indicator of structural condition should be adapted to the specific loading scenario. The corresponding Ib -values, categorized by load scenario, are summarized in Table 2.

Ib -value tensile RT	Ib -value tensile ET	Ib -value bending RT	Ib -value bending ET	Structural condition
$Ib > 0.1$	$Ib > 0.1$	$Ib > 0.1$	$Ib > 0.1$	No/slight damage
$0.1 > Ib > 0.07$	$0.1 > Ib > 0.08$	$0.1 > Ib > 0.07$	$0.1 > Ib > 0.075$	Moderate damage
$0.07 > Ib > 0.06$	$0.08 > Ib > 0.07$	$0.07 > Ib > 0.06$	$0.075 > Ib > 0.065$	Severe damage
$0.06 > Ib$	$0.07 > Ib$	$0.06 > Ib$	$0.065 > Ib$	Near to fracture

Table 2: Structural health assessment criteria based on Ib -values for repurposed EoL composites under different loading conditions.

Based on these criteria, the following assumptions can be made:

- If the structural condition is classified as moderately damaged, repair of the monitored structure is recommended.
- If the Ib -value indicates severe damage, structural replacement should be considered as a viable option.
- If the structure approaches fracture, safety concerns arise, and immediate intervention may be necessary.
- If loading conditions are considered in the interpretation of the Ib -value, the feasibility of Ib -value analysis for SHM of repurposed GFRP beams is further supported.

4 DISCUSSIONS

The results demonstrate that the Ib -value exhibits a consistent decreasing trend, independent of the applied loading condition. This observation supports the reliability and repeatability of Ib -value analysis across both tensile and bending load scenarios. Since second life applications of composite components may involve varying dominant loading scenarios, this dependency must be carefully considered when employing the Ib -value as a structural health indicator. Notably, final failure in all cases occurred at an Ib -value of approximately 0.06, suggesting that this value may serve as a threshold indicator of critical damage. Under ET conditions, the final Ib -values tended to be slightly higher than those observed at RT. This behavior likely reflects the combined influence of increased microcrack generation and thermal softening of the matrix. Given the comparable internal structural conditions of the specimens, it is reasonable to attribute the dominant effect to the latter, indicating that matrix weakening under ET contributes more significantly to the observed increase in Ib -value.

This study advances the current understanding of the Ib -value approach by examining its response not only to different loading modes but also to variations in temperature. The ability of the Ib -value to capture damage evolution under these diverse conditions highlights its potential as a robust diagnostic tool for SHM.

However, this study also has certain limitations. Notably, the behavior of the Ib -value under cyclic bending loading, especially beyond the onset of phase 2 (where damage localization becomes dominant), remains unexplored. Future research should address this aspect and explore the scalability of the approach, for example, by applying it to larger structural elements such as 1000 mm long spar cap beams. Additionally, validating the technique across different composite components from EoL WTBs would support a broader assessment of its applicability for SHM in sustainable energy infrastructure.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study presents an AE-based structural integrity assessment of EoL WTB components subjected to varying loading and temperature conditions. Key AE features, namely peak amplitude, cumulative hits, and centroid frequency, are evaluated in accordance with established failure analysis methodologies. Compared to RT specimens, ET specimens exhibit slightly reduced UTS and UFS, reflecting temperature-dependent material degradation.

In the b -/ Ib -value analysis, a representative segment extraction method based on mean values is introduced. The results show that the b -value does not exhibit a consistent trend over the specimen lifetime, limiting its reliability. In contrast, the Ib -value demonstrates a more robust and reproducible response, establishing it as a more reliable indicator of structural degradation.

Regardless of the specific form a monitoring criterion may take, the findings highlight the need for standardized methods to track the evolution of dominant crack regions during progressive failure. As the repurposing of composite materials gains increasing relevance, SHM approaches tailored to previously serviced materials under different loading conditions are essential. In particular, ensuring the structural integrity of components during the early stages of their second application is critical. The extended Ib -value approach proposed in this study provides a promising foundation for SHM of repurposed composites and shows potential for practical implementation in industrial sectors such as wind energy and construction.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Liu and C. Y. Barlow, Wind turbine blade waste in 2050, *Waste management (New York, N.Y.)*, **62**, 2017, pp. 229–240 (doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2017.02.007).
- [2] P. Johst, M. Bühl, C. Enderle, R. Kupfer, N. Modler and R. Böhm, Forecasting wind turbine blade waste with material composition and geographical distribution: Methodology and application to Germany, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, **211**, 2024 (doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107876).
- [3] J. Beauson, A. Laurent, D. P. Rudolph and J. Pagh Jensen, The complex end-of-life of wind turbine blades: A review of the European context, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, **155**, 2022 (doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2021.111847).
- [4] L. Mishnaevsky, K. Branner, H. N. Petersen, J. Beauson, M. McGugan and B. F. Sørensen, Materials for Wind Turbine Blades: An Overview, *Materials*, **10**, 2017 (doi: 10.3390/ma10111285).
- [5] Y. Yang, R. Boom, B. Irion, D.-J. van Heerden, P. Kuiper and H. de Wit, Recycling of composite materials, *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, **51**, 2012, pp. 53–68 (doi: 10.1016/j.cep.2011.09.007).
- [6] J. Potting, M. Hekkert, E. Worrell, and A. and Hanemaaijer, Circular Economy: Measuring innovation in the product chain, Accessed: Jan. 25, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2016-circular-economy-measuring-innovation-in-product-chains-2544.pdf>
- [7] K. Ruane *et al.*, Construction and Cost Analysis of BladeBridges Made from Decommissioned FRP Wind Turbine Blades, *Sustainability*, **15**, 2023 (doi: 10.3390/su15043366).
- [8] P. Johst *et al.*, Identification and Environmental Assessments for Different Scenarios of Repurposed Decommissioned Wind Turbine Blades, *Mater Circ Econ*, **5**, 2023 (doi: 10.1007/s42824-023-00085-7).
- [9] P. Johst *et al.*, Concept and Life Cycle Assessment of a Tiny House Made from Root Section Structures of a Decommissioned Large-Scale Wind Turbine Blade as a Repurposed Application, *Mater Circ Econ*, **6**, 2024 (doi: 10.1007/s42824-023-00093-7).
- [10] J. Joustra, B. Flipsen and R. Balkenende, Structural reuse of wind turbine blades through segmentation, *Composites Part C: Open Access*, **5**, 2021 (doi: 10.1016/j.jcomc.2021.100137).
- [11] M. Kucher, P. Johst, M. Lizaranzu, F. Lahuerta and R. Böhm, A Micromechanical Modeling Approach for the Estimation of the Weathering-Induced Degradation of Wind Turbine Blades, *Mater Circ Econ*, **5**, 2023 (doi: 10.1007/s42824-023-00088-4).
- [12] D. Jung and W. Na, Acoustic Emission Testing and Ib-Value Analysis of Ultraviolet Light-Irradiated Fiber Composites, *Applied Sciences*, **11**, 2021 (doi: 10.3390/app11146550).
- [13] D. Jung, W.-R. Yu and W. Na, Use of acoustic emission b(Ib)-values to quantify damage in composites, *Composites Communications*, **22**, 2020 (doi: 10.1016/j.coco.2020.100499).

- [14] P. Johst, S. Lee, E. Kim, S. Bae, R. Böhm and W. Na, Structural integrity assessment of repurposed wind turbine blade composite components with acoustic emission testing and Ib-value analysis, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **301**, 2025 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.112490).
- [15] H. Suzuki, T. Kinjo, Y. Hayashi, M. Takemoto and K. Ono, Wavelet transform of acoustic emission signals, *Journal of acoustic emission*, 1996, pp. 69–84.
- [16] B. Gutenberg, The energy of earthquakes, *QJGS*, **112**, 1956, pp. 1–14 (doi: 10.1144/GSL.JGS.1956.112.01-04.02).
- [17] T. Schumacher, C. C. Higgins and S. C. Lovejoy, Estimating Operating Load Conditions on Reinforced Concrete Highway Bridges with b-value Analysis from Acoustic Emission Monitoring, *Structural Health Monitoring*, **10**, 2011, pp. 17–32 (doi: 10.1177/1475921710365424).
- [18] T. Shiotani, X. Luo, H. Haya and M. Ohtsu, Damage quantification for concrete structures by improved b-value analysis of AE *Proceedings of the International Conference on Fracture, Italy, October 1, 2005*.